

BENEFITS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES THROUGH ROLE-PLAYING ACTIVITIES

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Abstract. For non-native speakers, learning a foreign language is always difficult; in these situations, several strategies can help to lessen this difficulty for both students and teachers. Role-playing games are among the most entertaining and beneficial pastimes. Individuals' personal development, communication skills, problem-solving ability, and empathy are all significantly impacted by role-playing exercises. Participants can explore various viewpoints, attitudes, and emotions by taking on a fictitious role and acting out events in these exercises. Here, we go into great length about the benefits and drawbacks of role-playing games.

Key words: cooperation, information gap activities, linguistic proficiency, communicative competency, fluency, role-playing, and simulations.

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ С ПОМОЩЬЮ РОЛЕВЫХ ИГР

Аннотация. Для тех, кто не является носителем языка, изучение иностранного языка всегда сопряжено с трудностями; в таких ситуациях несколько стратегий могут помочь уменьшить эту трудность как для студентов, так и для преподавателей. Ролевые игры - одно из самых занимательных и полезных времяпрепровождений. Упражнения в ролевых играх оказывают значительное влияние на личностное развитие людей, коммуникативные навыки, способность решать проблемы и сопереживание. Участники могут исследовать различные точки зрения, установки и эмоции, беря на себя вымышленную роль и разыгрывая события в этих упражнениях. Здесь мы подробно рассказываем о преимуществах и недостатках ролевых игр.

Ключевые слова: сотрудничество, деятельность, связанная с информационным разрывом, владение языком, коммуникативная компетентность, свободное владение языком, ролевые игры и симуляции.

Many educators have spoken about the effectiveness of the role-play technique in language instruction, but Maxwell may have provided the most thorough summary of the benefits of using role-play. Maxwell says that the essence of role-play is role-play, which can help students improve their language skills, increase their motivation and interest, and enable teachers to teach the language as well as cultural awareness.

Based on research by Maxwell and other academics, the following list of benefits of role-playing in language instruction:

- 1) It enables students to learn and practice the target language in meaningful context.
- 2) It improves students' different skills needed for the language acquisition process.
- 3) It motivates students to be interested and involved in learning.
- 4) It creates low-anxiety learning environments for students.
- 5) It offers students a variety of experiences and improves their 4 language skills.

6) It helps to improve students' cultural and nonverbal behavior.

In order to analyze the effective ways of implementing role play activities in teaching foreign languages we made a survey among the teachers and students of higher and primary educational schools. The reason of choosing teachers and students for the survey is that we want to analyze the results from two aspects.

While having the questionnaire we asked the questions from teachers and students of the Bukhara State University, school concerning the need of using role play activities in every type of the lesson.

Besides, we asked which type of role play activity they would prefer, for instance: cooperative role playing, conflict role playing, information gap role playing, and task based role playing. While most students chose cooperative and information gap role play activities, teachers mostly chose cooperative, conflict and information gap role play activities. Because they consider that these two types of role playing activities enhance students not only speaking skills, but also their critical thinking and point of view.

Van Ments summarized the advantages of role-play on attitudes and feelings of the students as follows¹;

- Enables students to express hidden feelings.
- Enables student to discuss private issues and problems.
- Enables student to empathize with others and understand their motivations.
- Gives practice in various types of behavior.
- Portrays generalized social problems and dynamics of group interaction, formal and informal.
- Gives life and immediacy to academic descriptive material.
- Role plays are motivational and effective because it involves activity.
- Provides feedback for teacher and student.
- It is student- centered.
- Closes gap between training and real life situations.
- They change attitudes.
- Permits training in the control of feelings and emotions.

Another question of the survey was connected with effectiveness of implementing role play activities with the mixed ability students. Most of the teachers consider that when the difficult parts of the task is adopted, or when the teacher can organize the roles according to their abilities, the result will be much more effective than expected, because each little attempt will improve learners' acting and speaking skills.

About the challenges of implementing role-play activities we can conclude from our survey that some students are not reluctant to play their part, they can be too involved in their roles that the lesson will be noisy and the teacher cannot manage the class.

Role playing is the best way to develop the skills of initiative, communication, problem-solving, self-awareness, and working cooperatively in teams, and it can be seen as an interaction

¹ Van Ments, M. The effective use of role-play: A handbook for teachers and trainers. New York: Nichols Publishing.1989

between play, games and simulations and the student that performs an activity with learning outcomes. Implementation of role playing activities:

1. encourages students to create their own reality;
2. develops the ability to interact to other people;
3. increases students motivation;
4. engages shy students in class activities;
5. makes students self - confident;
6. helps students to identify and correct misunderstandings;
7. is agreeable and fun;
8. shows students that the real world is complex and problems that appear in the real world cannot be solved by simply memorizing information;
9. underlines the simultaneous use of different skills.

There are also some other reasons of importance of using role play activities:

- it give students an understanding of their own learning by creating their own role-plays;
- can teach about ethical and moral issues arising from the science curriculum;
- it helps students to recognize and interpret their place in the world;
- it gives to the students a chance to experience life events in a physical way that is more appropriate to their own learning style;

Learning with role-playing enables students to reduce their anxiety while they gain confidence, they have a better professional know-how when they understand the situations, roles and questions asked or to be asked, the answers they should give,

and how to actively listen. These abilities are gained because role-playing allows repetition and the acquisition of reflexes and habits.

Role-playing encourages the participants to understand group dynamics and personal freedom, sharpens perception and encourages creativity and self-fulfillment.

Role-play is an effective technique to energize the teaching and learning atmosphere, arouse the interests of learners, and make the language acquisition impressive. So this research will mainly focus on how to apply it successfully and take the most advantage of it in English class.

The outcome shows there are some crucial factors for its success:

- the topic chosen should be real and relevant;
- the teacher need 'feed-in' the appropriate language;
- correct errors in a proper way;

Role-playing in the classroom gives variety, a change of pace, and plenty of chances for plenty of language production while also being a lot of fun!

Like other instructional methods, role-playing has its drawbacks. It could have issues that would be problematic in the classroom.

The following could serve as a summary of the issues with present role-play implementation and the actual issues faced by students in the classroom:

1. Problems with Current Situation

Both in teacher college and in the schools where they work, there is a dearth of professional and theoretical preparation for teachers employing role-play. Their primary training resources

included general introductions to communicative language practices, such as role-playing with a few phrases, or seeing seasoned teachers use role-playing.

2. *Pedagogical Problems in the Classroom*

Some methodologists summarized the disadvantages of using role-play into different categories:

- the lack of classroom space;
- cost of a lot of classroom time, students' play acting, chaos in the classroom;
- the lack of grammar work;
- lack of enough opportunities to participate.

In order to solve the above –mentioned problems and to avoid classroom chaos teachers must not use too difficult or too emotionally loaded role-plays, they must emphasize the evaluation criteria for their students and try to make the activity more effective for their students .

The most thorough studies on the potential drawbacks of role-play have been made by Van Ments. He offered the following list of the potential drawbacks of the usage of role-play²:

- 1) Teacher loses control over what is learnt and the order in which it is learned.
- 2) Simplifications can mislead.
- 3) Uses a large amount of time.
- 4) Uses other resources-people, space, special items.
- 5) Depends on the quality of tutor and student.
- 6) Impact may trigger withdrawal or defense symptoms.
- 7) May be seen as too entertaining or frivolous.
- 8) May dominate learning to the exclusion of solid theory and facts.
- 9) May depend on what students already know.

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